

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of Some Substituted 2-Phenyl-3-Arylquinazol-4-ones

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A series of substituted 2-phenyl-3-arylquinazol-4-ones (9-26) have been synthesised starting with substituted 2-phenyl-3-(3-hydroxy-4-carboxyphenyl)quinazol-4-ones (5-7). All the compounds have been evaluated for their *in vitro* growth inhibitory activity against the bacteria *E. coli*, *B. subtilis* and *X. citri* and the fungi *A. flavus* and *F. semitectum*. Compounds 9 and 23-26 showed marked antibacterial and antifungal activities.

AMONG the several classes of compounds reported to possess marked antimicrobial activity a number of quinazol-4-one derivatives¹⁻³ have been found to exhibit high activity against a wide variety of microbes parasitizing men and animals. The powerful antimicrobial activity associated with 4-aminosalicylic acid⁴ prompted us to synthesise substituted 2-phenyl quinazol-4-ones carrying the 4-aminosalicylic acid pharmacophore and its derivatives at 3-position which might also show synergistic activity. The present communication describes the synthesis and antimicrobial activity of substituted 2-phenyl-3-arylquinazol-4-ones (5-7 and 9-26).

Reaction of 2-phenyl-6,8-disubstituted benzoxazin-4-ones (1-3)⁵, prepared by cyclisation of the corresponding anthranilic acids⁶ with benzoyl chloride, with 4-aminosalicylic acid (4) afforded substituted 2-phenyl-3-(3-hydroxy-4-carboxyphenyl)quinazol-4-ones (5-7). Esterification of 5-7 using ethyl alcohol and sulphuric acid yielded the corresponding esters (9-11) in poor yields. Alternatively 1-3 were treated with ethyl 4-amino-2-hydroxy benzoate (8)⁷ to give 9-11 in good yields.

Acetylation and aroylation of 5-7 using acetic anhydride and aroylchlorides resulted in smooth formation of corresponding 2-phenyl-3-(3-acetoxy/aroxyloxy-4-carboxyphenyl)quinazol-4-ones (12-20). Treatment of 5-7 with aqueous bromine led to decarboxylation and tribromination of the substrates to yield corresponding 2-phenyl-3-(2,4,6-tribromo-3-hydroxyphenyl)quinazol-4-ones (21-23). Use of bromine in CS₂, instead of aqueous bromine in the above reaction resulted in the formation of 2-phenyl-3-(2,6-dibromo-3-hydroxy-4-carboxyphenyl)quinazol-4-ones (24-26) instead of decarboxylation, but in poor yields. Better yields of 24-26 were obtained when 5-7 were treated with bromine in acetic acid.

Experimental

The structure of all the compounds was checked by ir recorded on Perkin-Elmer 157 infracord

spectrometer. The pmr spectra were taken on a Varian EM-360 spectrometer using TMS as internal reference. The purity of all the compounds was checked on silica gel-G plates using iodine vapours as visualising agent. Melting points were taken in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected.

Substituted anthranilic acids and 2-phenyl-benzoxazin-4-ones were prepared by the methods of Wheeler *et al*⁶ and Sammour *et al*⁵, respectively.

2-Phenyl-3-(3-hydroxy-4-carboxyphenyl)quinazol-4-one (5): A mixture of 2-phenyl benzoxazin-4-one (1) (4.5 g; 0.02 mol) and 4-aminosalicylic acid (4) (3.0 g; 0.02 mol) in pyridine (20 ml) was refluxed for 9 hr. Solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the resulting solution was cooled, treated with 4 N HCl and heated on a water bath for 4 hr. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from methanol. Yield 6 g (80%), m.p. 215°. IR ν_{\max} (KBr): 3475 (-OH phenolic), 3250, (-OH carboxylic hydrogen bonded), 1650 (-COOH and -CON), 1600 (-C=N). PMR (DMSO-d₆): δ 6.40-8.20 (complex multiplet, 13H, Ar-H, except 8H of quinazolone, OH and COOH), 8.50 (dd, 1H, 8H of quinazolone). (Found: C, 70.41; H, 3.52; N, 7.65. C₂₁H₁₄N₂O₄ requires C, 70.39; H, 3.9; N, 7.82%).

Similarly compounds 6 and 7 were synthesised by treating the corresponding benzoxazin-4-ones (2-3) with 4-aminosalicylic acid.

2-Phenyl-3-(3-hydroxy-4-carbomethoxyphenyl)quinazol-4-one (9):

Method A: A solution of 5 (0.72 g; 0.002 mol) in absolute ethanol (20 ml) and conc. H₂SO₄ (5 ml) was refluxed for 18 hr. Solvent was removed *in vacuo* and treated with 10% aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution. The resulting sticky solid was separated, triturated with pet. ether (60-80°) to yield a crystalline solid, yield 0.15 g (20%), m.p. 90°.

Method B: A mixture of 1 (1.12 g; 0.005 mol) and ethyl 4-aminosalicylate (8) (0.9 g; 0.005 mol)

in pyridine (10 ml) was refluxed for 12 hr. Excess of pyridine was removed *in vacuo* and the residue taken in minimum amount of methanol and treated with 4 N HCl with cooling. The resulting solid filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from methanol, yield 1.4 g (70%), m.p. 90°. (Found : C, 71.35 ; H, 4.85 ; N, 7.39. $C_{28}H_{18}N_2O_4$ requires C, 71.5 ; H, 4.66 ; N, 7.25%).

Using the above methods compounds **10** and **11** were prepared by treating **2** and **3**, respectively with **8**.

2-Phenyl-3-(3-acetoxy-4-carboxyphenyl)quinazol-4-one (12) : A solution of **5** (0.72 g ; 0.002 mol) and sodium acetate (0.73 g ; 0.004 mol) in acetic anhydride (10 ml) was refluxed for 6 hr. Excess of acetic anhydride was distilled off and the residue poured on crushed ice and left overnight. The separated solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from methanol. Yield 0.62 g (67%), m.p. 118°. IR ν_{max} (KBr) : 3450 (-OH), 1770

(-O-C(=O)-CH₃). (Found : C, 69.4 ; H, 4.60 ; N, 7.39. $C_{28}H_{16}N_2O_5$ requires C, 69.0 ; H, 4.00 ; N, 7.0%).

Similarly, compounds **13** and **14** were prepared by acetylation of **6** and **7**, respectively.

2-Phenyl-3-(3-benzoyloxy-4-carboxyphenyl)quinazol-4-one (15) : A mixture of **5** (0.72 g ; 0.002 mol) and benzoylchloride (0.42 ml ; 0.003 mol) was shaken with 20% aqueous NaOH solution (10 ml) for 2 hr at room temp. The separated solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from methanol. Yield 0.6 g (66%), m.p. 230°. IR ν_{max} (KBr) : 3300

(-OH), 1725 (-O-C(=O)-Ph). (Found : C, 73.0 ;

H, 4.15 ; N, 6.37. $C_{28}H_{16}N_2O_5$ requires C, 72.72 ; H, 3.89 ; N, 6.06%).

Similarly, compounds **16** and **17** were prepared by benzoylation of **6** and **7**, respectively.

2-Phenyl-3-[3-(4-nitro-benzoyloxy)-4-carboxyphenyl]quinazol-4-one (18) : A mixture of **5** (0.72 g ; 0.002 mol) and 4-nitrobenzoyl chloride (0.55 g ; 0.003 mol) was shaken in dry pyridine (10 ml) for 2 hr and the separated solid filtered and treated with 10% aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution. The solid thus obtained was crystallised from methanol, yield 0.72 g (70%), m.p. 235°. (Found : C, 65.92 ; H, 3.48 ; N, 8.46. $C_{28}H_{17}N_3O_7$ requires C, 66.27 ; H, 3.35 ; N, 8.28%).

Using the above method compounds **19** and **20** were also prepared by reaction of **6** and **7** respectively with 4-nitrobenzoyl chloride.

2-Phenyl-3-(2,4,6-tribromo-3-hydroxyphenyl)quinazol-4-one (21) : Aqueous bromine (0.43 ml ; 0.008 mol) was added dropwise to a vigorously stirred solution of **5** (0.72 g ; 0.002 mol) in methanol (10 ml) during 15 min at room temp. After the addition, the reaction mixture was stirred for a further 15 min and the solid separated was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from methanol, yield 1.0 g (83%), m.p. 236°. IR ν_{max} (KBr) : 3200-3300 (-OH), 1670 (-C-N). PMR (DMSO-d₆) : δ 6.70-8.25 (complex multiplet, 10H, Ar-H, excluding 8H of quinazolone, -OH), 8.65 (dd, 1H, 8H of quinazolone). (Found : C, 43.75 ; H, 1.95 ; N, 5.12. $C_{20}H_{11}N_2O_2Br_3$ requires C, 43.56 ; H, 1.99 ; N, 5.08%).

Similarly, compounds **22** and **23** were prepared by bromination of **6** and **7**, respectively.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF SUBSTITUTED QUINAZOL-4-ONES

Compd. No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	N%* Found (Calcd.)
R ₄ = R ₅ = H								
5	H	H	COOH	OH	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	215	80	7.65 (7.82)
6	H	Br	COOH	OH	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄ Br	220	75	6.72 (6.40)
7	Br	Br	COOH	OH	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ Br ₂	202	78	5.65 (5.42)
9	H	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	OH	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₄	90	70	7.39 (7.25)
10	H	Br	COOC ₂ H ₅	OH	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ Br	125	68	6.30 (6.02)
11	Br	Br	COOC ₂ H ₅	OH	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ Br ₂	153	60	5.08 (5.14)
12	H	H	COOH	OCOCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₅	118	67	7.39 (7.0)
13	H	Br	COOH	OCOCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₅ Br	163	70	5.92 (5.84)
14	Br	Br	COOH	OCOCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₅ Br ₂	198	71	4.92 (5.01)
15	H	H	COOH	OCOC ₂ H ₅	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₅	230	66	6.37 (6.06)
16	H	Br	COOH	OCOC ₂ H ₅	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₅ Br	165	55	5.38 (5.17)
17	Br	Br	COOH	OCOC ₂ H ₅	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₅ Br ₂	200	58	4.60 (4.51)
18	H	H	COOH	OCOC ₂ H ₄ NO ₂ (4)	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₇	235	70	8.46 (8.28)
19	H	Br	COOH	OCOC ₂ H ₄ NO ₂ (4)	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₇ Br	175	68	7.08 (7.16)
20	Br	Br	COOH	OCOC ₂ H ₄ NO ₂ (4)	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₇ Br ₂	223	62	6.14 (6.30)
R ₄ = R ₅ = Br								
21	H	H	Br	OH	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Br ₂	236	83	5.12 (5.08)
22	H	Br	Br	OH	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ Br ₄	210	80	4.65 (4.44)
23	Br	Br	Br	OH	C ₂₀ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ Br ₆	255	82	3.98 (3.94)
24	H	H	COOH	OH	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ Br ₂	204	81	5.46 (5.42)
25	H	Br	COOH	OH	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ Br ₂	217	78	4.83 (4.71)
26	Br	Br	COOH	OH	C ₂₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄ Br ₄	210	68	3.63 (3.76)

* All the compounds also gave satisfactory C and H analysis.

2-Phenyl-3-(2,6-dibromo-3-hydroxy-4-carboxyphenyl)quinazol-4-one (24) :

Method A : A solution of bromine (0.27 ml ; 0.005 mol) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of **5** (0.72 g ; 0.002 mol) in carbon disulfide (10 ml) cooled in an ice-salt mixture. The separated solid was filtered and crystallised from methanol-water, yield 0.3 g, (30%), m.p. 204°.

Method B : A solution of bromine (0.27 ml ; 0.005 mol) in acetic acid (5 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred and ice cooled solution of **5** (0.72 g ; 0.002 mol) in acetic acid (10 ml). After the addition was over stirring was continued for further 30 min. The separated solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from methanol-water, yield 0.8 g (81%), m.p. 204°. IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : phenolic 3350-3450 (-OH phenolic and carboxylic

hydrogen bonded), 1650 (-COOH), 1635 (-C-N), 1600 (-C=N). PMR (DMSO-d₆) : δ 6.90-7.60 and 7.80-8.30 (complex multiplet 10H, Ar-H, excluding 8H of quinazolone and one proton *o*-to COOH) 7.65 (s, 1H, *o*-to COOH), 8.85 (dd, 1H, 8H of quinazolone). (Found : C, 45.8 ; H, 2.36 ; N, 5.72. C₂₁H₁₂N₂O₄Br₂ requires C, 45.35 ; H, 2.31 ; N, 5.4%).

Similarly compounds **25** and **26** were obtained by reaction of bromine with **6** and **7**, respectively.

Antimicrobial activity :

All the compounds have been evaluated for their *in vitro* growth inhibitory activity against the bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Xanthomonas citri*. A few representative compounds were also evaluated for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus flavus* and *Fusarium semitectum*.

Antibacterial assay: The antibacterial activity of compounds was examined by the agar diffusion technique⁹. In this method a standard 5 mm diameter sterilised filter paper disc impregnated with the compound (10 mg/ml of acetone) was placed on a agar plate seeded with the test organism. The plates were incubated for 24 hr at 37° and then observed for the zone of inhibition of bacterial growth around the disc. In each case three replications were performed.

Antifungal assay: The antifungal activity was evaluated by the agar growth technique⁹, which involves the mixing of toxicant with synthetic agar medium and allowing the planted fungus to grow on such poisoned food. The activity was determined at a concentration of 1 : 1,000 and the number of replications in each case was three. The average % inhibition after 7 days was calculated.

Results and Discussion

In the antibacterial test, the compounds in general showed moderate *in vitro* growth inhibitory activity. The best compounds of this series were 6, 7, 22, 23 and 25 which inhibited the growth of *E. coli*, *B. subtilis* and *X. citri* by 8-12 mm. In addition, compounds 17, 21 and 26 caused inhibition of growth of *E. coli* and *X. citri* of a similar order. The other compounds were inactive. Tetracycline used as standard gave inhibition of the growth of the above bacteria by 32, 36 and 40 mm, respectively.

In the antifungal assay, the compounds 5-7 and 21-26 inhibited the growth of *A. flavus* and *F. semitectum* by 16-54% while compounds 16 and 17 showed activity against *A. flavus* only and inhibited its growth by 91.6 and 50.2%, respectively. The best compounds of this series were 23-26 showing 33-54%

growth inhibitory activity against both the fungi. The control used for antifungal assay was acetone.

The antimicrobial assay results indicate that 2,3-diarylquinazol-4-ones in general possess better activity against the fungi than against the bacteria used. The antibacterial and antifungal activity is maximum when the 2-phenylquinazol-4-one is substituted by the bromine residues at 6 and 8 positions. The activity is still enhanced when bromine residue is at 2 and 6 positions of the phenyl ring at 3 position in quinazol-4-one.

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